

INTEGRATION ISSUES MYTHS IN THE WORKS OF SHARAF RASHIDOV

(Based on the example of "Song of Kashmir")

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Annotation:The article deals with the definition of the myth of different researchers, as well as the use of elements of the myth in the work of such Uzbek writer, statesman as Sharaf Rashidov. On the example of the story "Kashmir song" the author traces the principles of using mythological motives that perform certain artistic functions, act as a tool and technique.

Keywords: myth, mythology, poetics of myth, myth-making, legend, myth transformation

1.Introduction:The etymological word "myth" has an Indo-European root meudh-, mudh-, which in ancient times meant "to care about something", "to have something in mind", "to passionately desire something", etc. [8] Over time, due to the growing interest in this phenomenon, the meaning of this term begins to grow and expand. Already in the period of antiquity, the first attempts to understand the problem of mythologizing appeared in the works of such ancient philosophers as Plato [7] and Aristotle [1]: in Plato, myth had the meaning of "speech" or "opinion", while Aristotle gives this term the meaning of "plot", "story", "tale". Understanding the social role of myth becomes an object of attention in the Middle Ages. G. Vico [2] believes that myths are poetic stories generated by human fantasy.

The problem statement: Modern researchers of mythology consider myth from various points of view, among which one can observe a commonality of opinions:

M. Eliade notes that myth sets out a sacred history, narrates about an event that took place in memorable times "the beginning of all beginnings"; [11].

K. Levi-Strauss is of the opinion that every myth is a memory of past events; [3]

V. Toporov believes that myth always refers to events of the past: "before the creation of the world" or "at the beginning of time" - in any case, "long ago". [3, p. 214]

The tradition of using myths in poetic creativity has deep roots and sources. Studying the specifics of the literatures of the ancient world, one can note such an interesting fact as the oral origin and functioning in the form of myths, legends, parables, such grandiose ritual-mythological monuments as the Indian Vedas, the Iranian Avesta, the Jewish Bible, in various sources, including such literary monuments as "Avesta", "Bundakhshin", "Gathas" myths of the ancient peoples of Central Asia have been preserved.

Literature throughout its development has constantly turned to myth. The attitude to mythology, especially to the antique era, changed from era to era in accordance with the change in the general historical

and cultural situation. As M. Eliade notes: Myth is one of the extremely complex realities of culture and it can be studied and interpreted in the most numerous and complementary aspects. [11, p.15] Mythology is an expression of the only possible knowledge, which does not yet pose any questions about the reliability of what it knows, and therefore does not seek it.

Solution:In connection with the revival of the tradition of mythologizing in the literature of the peoples of Central Asia in the 50-90s, it is necessary to note the moral-philosophical, artistic-functional and aesthetic significance of this phenomenon. The study of the function of myth at the present stage is due to the wide and diverse use of the poetics of mythologizing in the works of such writers as Ch. Aitmatov, Sh. Rashidov, A. Mukhtar, T. Zulfikarov, O. Bokeev, A. Alimjanov. In the works of Uzbek writers, one can also trace the influence of the poetics of myth, an appeal to the traditions going deep into history in the Turkic-language literatures. At the same time, one can single out something in common that brings together the works of A. Mukhtar, Sh. Rashidov - this is the desire for a philosophical polyphonic reflection of reality, looking at the world through the prism of myths, legends, traditions. One of the writers and statesmen of Uzbekistan Sharaf Rashidov also turned to myths when creating his remarkable works "Kashmir Song" and "The Book of Two Hearts".

During his stay in India, Sh. Rashidov carefully studied the culture, art and literature of the Kashmiri people, and also visited the theater in Kashmir and watched the play "Bambur and Yambarzol". This play inspired the writer to create the story "Kashmir Song". Written in a short time, the story was published in 1956 in the 10th issue of the magazine "Sharq Yulduzi".

The story "Kashmir Song" is based on a Kashmiri folk legend. This is an inspired work glorifying pure love, unbending will to win, the triumph of truth. The plot of the work is deep and meaningful, it is the myth with its installation of showing the eternal struggle of the forces of good and evil that allows the author to reveal the idea of the victory of good over evil. The composition of the story is compressed and small in volume, includes a prologue, six parts and an afterword. The story is built on the basis of such mythological images as Nargis, Bambur, Atirgul, Lola, Navruzgul, personifying the forces of Good and Buran, Khorud, Whirlwind, representing the forces of Evil.

In the prologue, the author discusses the issue of the wisdom of the people, which originates in their memory. He says: "Memory is the consequence of wisdom, and it is the cause of it..."

In them is the memory of the people, which, expanding its banks, flows from generation to generation, in them is the wisdom of the people, which, like a torch that flares up on the way, is passed on from generation to generation." [10, p.333]

Turning to the topic of the wisdom and memory of the people, to its mythology, the author wants to note that the essence of things is largely identified with their origin, then knowledge of origin is the key to using a thing and knowledge of the past is identified with wisdom. [5, p.173]

If the prologue depicts the beautiful country of Kashmir and respect for its people, the reasons for writing this story, the writer's excitement, which he feels in his heart, then from the first chapter to the end, the plot of the myth of Nargis and Bambura is systematically located. The relationship between Nargis and Bambur, which is the basis of the story – friendship, love and loyalty, freedom and happiness – runs through the entire work like a red thread. Although all parts of the work are not very voluminous, the depicted events and actions, episodes are voluminous and real in their content, the generalizations coming from them are also deep and vital. The poetics of the myth allows the author, despite the fact that each part depicts individual events, to connect them into one common plot, each part is very closely connected with the next in its development. All events serve to reveal the main idea of the work – the depiction of the eternal struggle of good with evil, life and death, the victory of good and the eternity of life. It is mythology, the poetics of the

myth with their eternal leitmotif of the struggle between Good and Evil, and the final victory of the forces of Good that helps the writer achieve his goal.

Results and samples:

In creating the story "Kashmir Song" the writer turns to classical forms of mythology. In it the writer sang of love and fidelity reflected in the hearts of lovers, about whom the Kashmiri people kept in their souls and passed on from generation to generation for several centuries - their legends and myths. The writer depicts the beautiful and pure love of the snowdrop Nargis and the Shah of Bees Bahadur Bambura, as well as their symbolic struggle against the enemies Buran and Khorud. Through these events the author shows the historical past of the Kashmiri people, their life, dreams and aspirations, fate, joys and sorrows, as well as their selfless struggle against foreign conquerors. In depicting events, creating characters and images Sharaf Rashidov uses the technique of opposition. Through this technique of opposition he reveals the characters of the heroes. At the same time, their difference from each other becomes clearly visible. This can be traced in the positive image of Nargis. The author reveals the charming and tender image of Nargis to such an extent that she appears before the reader in all her beauty.

- Nargis was the first to blossom in the valley. And her beauty was incomparable - whoever saw her once, remembered her forever. Wearing a blue velvet jacket over a silk dress, tying her head with a white kerchief, putting on earrings made of precious dew, she swayed in the wind, intoxicated by the space, light, colors, songs. [10, p. 335]

Wanting to paint the image of Nargis, the artist was able to find the necessary colors - tender words and expressions. Because the author's focus is on the task of matching the external features of the image with its inner world. Along with the fact that the author reveals the image of Nargis very sincerely and with love, humanizes and endows her with human qualities. At the same time, he creates a number of positive images of Lola, Atirgul, Navruzgul.

- On the other side of the stone, the plump Lola rose, her leaves unfurling. [10, p.341]

- Atirgul rose above the green wave created by the wind, swaying the leaves. Like everything around her, with the arrival of spring, she blossomed, opened her buds to the sun, looked elegant, languid. [10, p.342]

And she thinks like a mythological character:

- Where flowers bloom,

Dreams come true,

And fairy tales come true

Where flowers bloom. [10, p.343]

It should be noted that the researcher of the poetics of myth E. Meletinsky, studying the influence of myth on literature, writes: "The fantastic images of mythology widely reflect the real features of the surrounding world. In this reflection of reality by myth there is even a special "completeness", because all more or less significant natural and social realities must be rooted in myth, find their origins, explanation and sanction in it, in a certain sense they must all have their own myth." [5, p. 170]

The author describes the image of Nargis with great skill, passion and warmth. Although it is just a flower, but with the help of the poetics of myth and personification, the flower is associated with a girl, with a lover, with sincere and pure love.

Along with the heroes - bearers of Good, the work contains opposing mythological images of the forces of Evil Buran and Khorud, which he creates with a feeling of hatred and rage.

- The blizzard is cruel, strong, but still love is stronger.

Khorud is powerful, but not over her.

Loving, I will overcome the mighty river's current,

Loving, I will pass alive through flame and sand.

More dangerous than Khorud, more terrible than boiling waters

To be silent when love calls to go and sing! [10, p.336]

- An icy whirlwind swept from one end to the other, chilling the flowers and leaves, sprinkling the buds and petals with poisonous dust. Death was coming, capable of taking many forms, but certain death in any of them.

- Having accumulated strength and fury, Buran returned.

When Buran appears as a mythological personification of the forces of evil, it becomes dark in the flower garden. All the plants in the flower garden tremble from his screams and bitter breath. But Buran cannot break the will of Nargis and her friends.

At the end of the work, feeling that his strength is leaving him and he cannot resist good, Khorud says the following:

I can beat and knock down,

Breaking the living thread.

I have been fighting for centuries -

Why is this thread strong? [10, p.361]

Neither Buran nor Khorud, symbolizing Evil, can understand what the true power of Good is. In the plot of the story "Kashmir Song" we can trace how the mythological images of Buran and Khorud bring many troubles to the Flower Garden, personifying the pure love of Nargis and her friends. And although they suffer a lot of torment, their faith in justice and the ultimate victory of good helps them to withstand all troubles very steadfastly, since they believe that their savior Bambur will come and save them from all troubles, from darkness and oppression. Therefore, Nargis and her friends do not surrender to mythological monsters, they respond to them with struggle and faith in a happy future.

A special place in the plot of the work is occupied by the trials that the hero-savior Bambur undergoes. This is a hero who demonstrates his strength and his fortitude on the way to achieving his goal.

- I am the king of bees, - Bambur finally said when he found the gift of speech. - I have flown over many gardens and flower beds, mountain slopes and deserts, fertile meadows and rich fields. But I have never met anyone like you. You may not believe it, but I have been looking for you. I have been looking for so many years! ... I have found the meaning of my life - it is you, Nargis. Do not reject me - my death is in your rejection, Nargis! [10, p.338]

To create imagery and expressiveness in the story, the writer uses myth as a way of modeling historical reality. At the same time, myth, as E. Meletinsky notes: "...creates a certain new fantastic "higher

reality”, which is paradoxically perceived by the bearers of the corresponding mythological tradition as the primary source and ideal prototype (i.e. “archetype”, but not in the Jungian, but in the broadest sense of the word) of these life forms. Modeling turns out to be a specific function of myth.” [5, p.171]

The story contains only one conflict: it is a conflict between two inflexible (incompatible) mythological forces of Good and Evil, which is refracted onto the reality of the struggle of the oppressed class against the oppressors.

Conclusion:

The story "Kashmir Song" by Sharaf Rashidov has earned the attention of readers with its high ideological content, artistic maturity, the reality of the events depicted through the prism of mythologism and the fullness of mythological images that reveal the historical realities of the life of the Indian people. The translation of the story into more than fifty languages of the world suggests that this is an achievement not only for the writer, but also a great success for Uzbek literature.

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